

Transform2Open

Workflow Optimization

A Handout for Efficient
Open Access Processes

Report

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Transform2Open

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Abstract

This handout supports practitioners seeking to design more effective and efficient open access workflows. It draws on findings from the DFG-funded project Transform2Open, summarizing insights from a literature review and expert interviews. Based on these, it offers concrete recommendations to further develop and optimize existing processes.

Introduction

The following report was produced by Transform2Open, a project supported by the German Research Foundation (*Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft*, DFG) and dedicated to the further development of budgets, criteria, competency profiles, and other processes at research institutions related to the financial aspects of the open access transformation. It contains recommendations for how German academic libraries — at universities, universities of applied sciences (FH, *Fachhochschulen*), and research performing organizations (RPOs, *außeruniversitäre Forschungseinrichtungen*) — can sustainably optimize their open access workflows while deploying personnel as effectively as possible.

In this report, open access processes are defined to include all aspects of an open access publication's life cycle as well as various financing and business models. In particular, these include:

- the negotiation, implementation, administration, and evaluation of open access publishing agreements, including publish and read agreements and gold open access agreements;
- the support and evaluation of diamond open access initiatives;
- the support and evaluation of pledging programs, including Subscribe to Open (S2O);
- the administration of publication funds, including associated reporting requirements; and

- the deposit of publications in institutional and disciplinary repositories, including self-archiving.

This report aims to provide a comprehensive series of recommendations, addressing itself most immediately to the concerns of German institutions. While it examines internationally-relevant topics, special care is taken to consider dynamics of immediate relevance to institutions within Germany. These include the administration of DEAL agreements and funder reporting, most significantly for the DFG’s Open Access Publication Funding program¹. In addition, this report contains recommendations relevant to both external as well as institutional publishers (for example, *Universitätsverlage*); however, publication workflows as such (e.g. single-source publishing or peer review workflows) are out of scope.² What follows is in no way to be understood as a how-to guide, such as already exist for aspects of open access workflows (such as the creation and maintenance of publication funds and information budgets, as well as repository deposit programs³). Instead, this report takes as its focus recommendations for the optimization of open access workflows as a whole.

1 See <https://www.dfg.de/en/research-funding/funding-opportunities/programmes/infrastructure/lis/funding-opportunities/open-access-publication-funding>.

2 For recommendations for institutional publishers, see the work of the Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Universitätsverlage at <https://ag-univerlage.de>.

3 Libraries can consult a wealth of literature when seeking to establish or streamline open access services and workflows at their institutions. For a recent example, with recommendations for embedding parts of these workflows in library acquisitions departments, see Rösch, H., Geschuhn, K., Barbers, I., Bove, K., Pohlmann, T. und Satzinger, L. (2022). Open Access ermöglichen. Open Access-Transformation und Erwerbung in wissenschaftlichen Bibliotheken. Ein praktischer Leitfaden. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6090208>. For literature regarding the establishment of a publication fund, see Bruch, C., Fournier, J., Pampel, H. (2014). Open-Access-Publikationsfonds. Eine Handreichung, Arbeitsgruppe Open Access der Schwerpunktinitiative, “Digitale Information” der Allianz der deutschen Wissenschaftsorganisationen. <https://doi.org/10.2312/allianzoa.006>. See also Pampel, H., Tullney, M. (2017). Open-Access-Publikationsfonds. In Söllner, K., Mittermaier, B. (Eds.), *Praxishandbuch Open Access* (Pp. 162–172). De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110494068-019>. As part of its work, Transform2Open has also created a modular tool to aid in the creation of an information budget, available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828013>. See footnote 5 for an approach to optimizing repository deposit workflows.

1 Information Gathering

To formulate the following recommendations, Transform2Open conducted a literature review and semi-structured interviews with representatives of seven academic libraries at a diverse set of research institutions throughout Germany. The following summarizes the information gathered through these two methods.

1.1 Literature Review

In early 2023, Transform2Open reviewed the available literature containing recommendations for the optimization of open access workflows. What follows highlights a subset of the sources consulted. Given the dynamic in the development of open access funding and business models, research literature often addresses opportunities for optimization of current and new open access workflows and their challenges in a fragmentary manner and tailored to specific situations.⁴ In light of this, the following review includes both literature that addresses current challenges as well as earlier contributions that provide valuable insight into work already undertaken to optimize workflows in the past.

In her 2014 article on streamlining the deposit of scholarly articles in institutional repositories, Shannon Kipphut-Smith notes that “[a] workflow is only successful if it is *manageable* and *realistic*”.⁵ Furthermore, she acknowledges that “the evolving nature of the open access environment necessitates that the work-

4 Open access publications and workflows have existed since the advent of repositories and the first open access journals in the early 1990s. Nevertheless, the rapid pace of innovation in the field of open access means that new workflows have constantly needed to be established. Examples of this are the workflows introduced with the first publish and read agreements (then known as offsetting), or those that emerged and were adapted with the growth of the S2O model.

5 Kipphut-Smith, S. (2014). “Good Enough”. Developing a Simple Workflow for Open Access Policy Implementation. *College & Undergraduate Libraries* 21 (3–4), 279–294, here 284, *emphasis added*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10691316.2014.932263>. In her article, Kipphut-Smith focuses on creating a library workflow for institutional repository deposit. For a similar approach to this workflow in the German-speaking world, see Vierkant, P., Siegert, O., Deinzer, G., Gebert, A., Herbstritt, M., Pampel, H., Tobias, R., Wagner, A. (2017). Workflows zur Bereitstellung von Zeitschriftenartikeln auf Open-Access-Repositoryen. Herausforderungen und Lösungsansätze. *O-Bib. Das Offene Bibliotheksjournal* 4 (1), 151–169. <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/2017H1S151-169>.

flow *adapt quickly* and be *flexible*”.⁶ Both observations remain key principles for optimization of open access workflows today.

In 2017 and 2018, representatives of the Max Planck Digital Library (MDPL) and Vienna University Library conducted multiple workshops to develop recommendations for the implementation of “offsetting agreements” (known today as “publish and read agreements”). The result, thoroughly described in an article by Kai Geschuhn and Graham Stone, was the introduction of the “ESAC Workflow Recommendations for Transformative and Open Access Agreements”.⁷ To this day, these and related recommendations⁸ remain the basis for the structuring of publish and read and similar agreements, such as those negotiated by the DEAL consortium. The ESAC recommendations demonstrate the importance of setting standards for metadata exchange and the verification of author affiliations for the successful execution of open access workflows; these standards create the preconditions for workflow automation, which in turn can lead to the reduction of administrative costs.

In a similar manner to the aforementioned ESAC recommendations, Claudia Frick’s contribution to the *Praxishandbuch Open Access* (Practical handbook for open access) addresses ways to optimize open access workflows.⁹ In it, she provides seven recommendations for the payment of publication charges, including the maximal utilization of normalized data (e.g. Persistent Identifiers or PIDs)¹⁰; centralized, one-time data entry; and a move from one-off, post-hoc APC

6 Kipphut-Smith, S. (2014). “Good Enough”. Developing a Simple Workflow for Open Access Policy Implementation. *College & Undergraduate Libraries* 21 (3–4), 279–294, here 285–6, *emphasis added*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10691316.2014.932263>.

7 Geschuhn, K., Stone, G. (2017). It’s the workflows, stupid! What is required to make ‘offsetting’ work for the open access transition. *USKG Insights* 30 (3), 103–118. <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.391>; see also Pinhasi, R., Blechl, G., Kromp, B., Schubert, B. (2018). The weakest link. Workflows in open access agreements. The experience of the Vienna University Library and recommendations for future negotiations. *USKG Insights* 31. <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.419>; The ESAC recommendations were updated in 2021 and are available at <https://esac-initiative.org/about/oa-workflows/>.

8 See Bruch, C., Deinzer, G., Geschuhn, K., Hätscher, P., Hillenkötter, K., Kreß, U., Pampel, H., Schäffler, H., Stanek, U., Timm, A., Wagner, A. (2015). Positions on creating an Open Access publication market which is scholarly adequate: Positions of the Ad Hoc Working Group Open Access Gold in the priority initiative “Digital Information” of the Alliance of Science Organisations in Germany. <https://doi.org/10.2312/allianzoa.009>; Pampel, H., Bertelmann, R., Hillenkötter, K., Mittermaier, B., Pieper, D., Schäffler, H., Seeh, S., Tullney, M. (2022). Recommendations for Transformative Journal Agreements with Providers of Publishing Services: Guidelines of the priority initiative “Digital Information” of the Alliance of Science Organisations in Germany, against the background of the implementation of the Open Access Strategy 2021–2025 of the Alliance of Science Organisations in Germany. <https://doi.org/10.48440/allianzoa.046>.

9 Frick, C. (2017): Empfehlungen für Workflows zur Übernahme von Publikationsgebühren. In Söllner, K. und Mittermaier, B. (Eds.), *Praxishandbuch Open Access* (Pp. 323–330). De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110494068-037>.

10 For a similar call in the same volume, see Müller, U. (2017): Standards und Best Practices im Kontext von Open Access. In Söllner, K., Mittermaier, B. (Eds.), *Praxishandbuch Open Access* (S. 56–59). De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110494068-007>.

payments to publisher agreements and collective invoicing.¹¹ Both Frick and the authors of the ESAC recommendations already recognized in the late 2010s that publisher agreements with open access components require scalable workflows made fit for an age where open access publication is standard.

More recent scholarship on open access workflows — as reflected in exemplary contributions from Sweden¹² and the United States¹³ — addresses questions such as the influence of agreement structure on author behavior (for example, the strategic selection of corresponding authors to avoid publication charges¹⁴) and the challenge of administering publisher agreements on a proliferating number of publisher-dependent tools such as dashboards¹⁵. Although some contributions continue to address agreements between institutions and individual publishers, the focus has shifted toward the challenges arising from the administration of an increasing number of agreements and multiple pledging programs with different conditions and an increasing number of dashboards. These articles reflect many of the successes, challenges, and concerns raised in the semi-structured interviews detailed below.

Even as the demands of open access workflows have persisted since the first contribution detailed here (2014) until now, the understanding of what open access workflows are and the challenges they pose continues to morph and evolve. Of special relevance to these present recommendations is the insight that successful open access workflows must remain manageable, realistic and flexible (Kipphut-Smith). In this spirit, automation, the prerequisite of which is the setting and use of standards and PIDs, can lead to optimized workflows, which in turn allows for the minimization of administrative costs (Geschuhn and Stone; Frick). Finally, the proliferation of publisher agreements with open access components and open access memberships, in Germany above all since the first DEAL agreement with Wiley in 2019, has required libraries to evaluate their open access processes as a cohesive whole instead of only focusing on the optimization of individual workflows — for instance, repository deposit or single publish and read agreements.

11 See here also Geschuhn, K., Sikora, A. (2015). Management von Article Processing Charges. Herausforderungen für Bibliotheken. *O-Bib. Das Offene Bibliotheksjournal* 2 (1), 27–34. <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/2015H1S27-34>.

12 Parmhed, S., Säll, J. (2023). Transformative agreements and their practical impact. A librarian perspective. *USKG Insights* 36. <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.612>

13 Scott, R. E. und Fernandez, M. (Eds.). (2024). Open Access. One Goal, Many Pathways [Special issue]. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 68 (1–2). <https://doi.org/10.5860/lrts.68n1>.

14 The increase in the number of corresponding authors per scholarly article is a key example of this. Due to criteria in many publish and read agreements that only apply when corresponding authors belong to the institution with said agreement, observers note the phenomenon of researchers' increasing strategic assignment of the corresponding author role.

15 See Goddard, M., Brundy, C. (2024). Open Access Workflows for Academic Libraries. *College & Research Libraries* 85 (4). <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.85.4.503>.

1.2 Interviews with Practitioners

In fall 2023, Transform2Open conducted semi-structured interviews with twelve library staff members responsible for open access workflows at seven German institutions of varying types and sizes.¹⁶ Interviews lasted approximately two hours and were conducted on the basis of a question catalog made available to participants in advance so as to provide them the opportunity to consult with their colleagues prior to their interviews (see Appendix 1). Although all precirculated questions were discussed during the interviews, the order varied depending on the structure of the workflows at each institution, with the focus placed on the chronological sequence of open access processes as carried out at the institution in question. To encourage open discussion and give the freedom to describe weaknesses as experienced in their open access workflows candidly, both interviewees and their institutions were granted anonymity.

With these interviews, Transform2Open aimed to investigate how open access workflows are implemented in practice while also creating a space for interviewees to develop ideas for optimized open access workflows and identify the conditions and structures necessary for their implementation.

In what follows, we present the findings of these interviews in detail. The first section highlights three dynamics participants identified when describing their experiences of open access workflows. We then outline a generalized representation of open access workflows in order to discuss three challenges that exist across multiple, and sometimes even all, interviewed institutions. While the dynamics outline the conditions and room within which academic libraries can maneuver with regard to open access workflows, the challenges highlight areas in which possibilities for optimization are sought.

1.2.1 Three Dynamics Underpinning Open Access Workflows

The following dynamics summarize general trends that emerged from both Transform2Open's interviews and the literature review. Given the diverse landscape of academic libraries in Germany, these should be seen as general statements that helped guide the formulation of coherent recommendations, but do not apply in equal measure to all libraries or institutions.

¹⁶ Representatives from institutions in six federal states were interviewed, including a research performing organization, a state and university library, a university of applied sciences (*Fachhochschule*) and four university libraries. They represented institutions with a publication output ranging from approximately 70 to about 7,500 publications per year, according to data from Open Access Monitor. Six out of seven interviews were conducted via Zoom; one took place in person at the interviewees' institution.

DYNAMIC 1:

Open access workflows emerge through the interaction of various stakeholders, including publishers, libraries, research funders, infrastructure providers, and researchers.

Open access workflows are the result of decisions of, and shaped by, multiple stakeholders, including:

- **Publishers and their workflows,**
for example, the kind of data a publisher makes available and in what form, whether it be on a dashboard or Excel files sent at regular intervals,
- **Intermediary infrastructure providers,**
for example, Crossref and its metadata schema, which enables institutions to represent certain metadata fields,
- **External research funders, such as grant agencies and their guidelines and policies,**
for example, stipulations as found in grant and reporting requirements, such as the DFG's Open Access Publication Funding program,
- **Libraries as well as their parent institutions and their organizational structures,**
for example, a decentralized university with distributed decision-making authority and corresponding budgetary structures, or a research performing organization with clearly established lines of reporting and centralized budgetary authority,
- **Researchers as readers and authors (whose priorities are shaped by existing incentive structures within academia),**
for example, researchers who expect access to certain journals or the ability to publish within them at “no cost” and who therefore advocate for institutional agreements with relevant publishers.

Characteristic of this system is that no single group holds full decision-making authority: each of the named groups operates within its own institutional and/or commercial boundaries and possesses a limited ability to act. Individual stakeholders also have limited room to act within their institutions due to specific characteristics of these institutions. A concrete example is the centralized payment of open access fees by the library — where possible without the direct involvement of researchers. While such a measure might be seen as an optimized workflow, this was not always feasible due to the decentralized structure of some

interviewed institutions and their budgetary structures. Moreover, requiring researchers to share in publication costs — despite the added administrative workload — might be desirable, as it could promote greater cost awareness among researchers.

As open access workflows are embedded in a global scholarly publishing system, optimization strategies must account for both local conditions and sometimes conflicting interests. No single stakeholder can bring about comprehensive workflow optimization alone — change requires coordination among all stakeholders. Successful change requires the use of existing incentives to win over stakeholders for sustainable improvements.

DYNAMIC 2:

Libraries' open access workflows have mostly developed organically and are often distributed across multiple departments.

At the institutions interviewed, many open access workflows have evolved over time in response to specific events, such as new agreement models, policies, and funding programs, like the DFG's Open Access Publication Funding program, and were adapted to the resulting needs.

Initially, these efforts often began as secondary tasks undertaken by committed individuals or small teams who advocated for open access among researchers and library staff. These individuals frequently operated outside of established organizational structures and workflows. As open access grew in importance and the administrative demands of publish and read agreements — for example with DEAL — increased, open access became a central part of library processes. The pace of engagement with this change varies: while some institutions are actively working to streamline their processes, others still lack an end-to-end approach to their open access workflows.

DYNAMIC 3:

Open access publishing requires not only financial, but also (considerable) human resources from libraries. Despite the considerable workload that open access workflows entail, libraries are rarely granted additional positions to handle these tasks; moreover, advertised positions are sometimes difficult to fill.

In interviews, library staff emphasized the administrative burden of managing open access processes. Of the seven institutions interviewed, only one reported creating a new position for these workflows. Institutions without new positions tackle the additional workload with existing staff — in many cases by assigning

them more duties or repurposing open positions before advertising them. Filling open access positions has proven difficult in many places due to a lack of qualified applicants.

1.2.2 Depiction of Open Access Workflows in Practice

As previously outlined, the (open access) workflows at interviewees' institutions developed historically in response to local needs and externally imposed parameters. In our interviews, the following characteristics of these workflows were particularly prominent:

The first level (Fig. 1) follows the path to publication of a single academic work. The institutional workflow within the library often begins at the pre-submission phase. Here, the focus is primarily on publicizing and promoting existing (or new) agreements, such as publish and read agreements or memberships. Funding approval for open access and associated publication fees is also granted, should a manuscript be accepted. The second phase involves the submission of a manuscript, peer review, and acceptance for publication. Open access workflows during this phase can include the verification of the corresponding author's affiliation, as well as the submission, review, and approval of publication fund applications. In the post-publication phase, open access workflows can involve agreement monitoring, repository deposit, payment of publication fees, and funder reporting. Throughout the entire process — from submission to publication — libraries assist researchers, answering questions related to open access approval procedures, institutional affiliation, and the payment of publication charges.

While the first level depicts a single publication's lifecycle, the second level (Fig. 2) depicts the negotiation, management, and assessment of offers for open access memberships, pledging programs, and publish and read agreements. In some cases, these workflows also occur at the consortial level. Yet even when consortia take on these tasks in whole or in part, libraries at individual institutions must decide which publishing agreements to renew or join.

Figure 1. Generalized open access workflow for an individual publication¹⁷

Figure 2. Generalized open access workflow for agreements, etc.

17 These two diagrams were initially created as part of the “Library Workflows” subgroup of the NISO Open Access Business Processes Working Group. We thank this subgroup, particularly Caroline Coward, Tamar Fuches, and Maureen Walsh, for the discussions and critical questions, especially regarding the interrelationship between these two diagrams.

Not all publications and agreements/programs encompass all aspects of the workflows detailed above. For an open access article published in a journal with a Subscribe to Open¹⁸ or other pledging model, the individual publication workflow might require an annual payment and promotion, as well as the advising and reporting steps; on the second level, the library might regularly evaluate whether the institution should continue to support these programs. In contrast, a publication, for example with Wiley, that is managed through the DEAL consortium, might include more of the steps described above, including agreement promotion and regular verification of authors' funding eligibility. Additionally, it might involve processing publication fund requests for articles in gold open access journals and monitoring. This clearly shows how much the type of open access model influences workflows and workload.

1.2.3 Three Key Challenges for Open Access Workflows

In discussions with interviewees, three main challenges, which are also reflected in the diagrams (Fig. 1 and 2), repeatedly came to the fore:

CHALLENGE 1:

Due to the heterogeneous publishing landscape, experts interviewed emphasize that advising authors remains a significant challenge.

Different publication and funding models with varying terms and workflows require extensive clarification. One institution-wide publish and read agreement might only cover hybrid publishing with the publisher in question, while another agreement might cover both gold and hybrid publications. In some cases, hybrid publications are paid for with a one-time annual sum, whereas gold publications are billed per unit and might possibly need to be covered by a publication fund. For another publication — such as an article in a Subscribe to Open journal — there might not be any specialized workflow needed. The differences depending on publisher and model entail a high expenditure of resources for libraries, especially in the form of time-consuming communication with researchers. For them, the specific details of each agreement are often difficult to understand.

18 For a library perspective on Subscribe to Open, see Brundy, C., Steel, G. (2021). Subscribe to Progress. Advancing Equity Through Openness. Reflecting and encouraging the acceleration of open practices in scholarship, *Common Place, Series 1.2: Business of Knowing*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/6ffd8432.20811f1e>. Brundy and Steel welcome that: “S2O allows librarians a straightforward way to encourage publishers to convert entire subscription journals to open without having to create major new workflows [...] such as those required by APC-based open access agreements.”

CHALLENGE 2:

Current workflows are often characterized by redundancies, as exemplified in metadata entry.

With one exception, interviewed institutions lack a single system that enables the automated reuse of information collected during the submission and approval phases throughout all steps up to reporting. Instead, information provided in a publisher's dashboard is sometimes simultaneously entered by an author into a publication fund application, approved and supplemented by library staff, later added to with information only available upon publication (such as the DOI), and then copied and pasted into an additional reporting table for the DFG's Open Access Publication Funding program. For most institutions, open access workflows from submission to post-publication require the manual entry or transfer of publication metadata row by row across multiple systems at multiple stages. In brief, automated data transfer is largely absent from these workflows. Instead, they rely on frequent manual interventions with a correspondingly high risk of errors.

CHALLENGE 3:

The multitude of publisher platforms as well as intermediary tools and dashboards entail a substantial workload.

With the growing number of open access agreements, the number of platforms, dashboards, and other tools needed to manage these agreements has also increased. As a result, a large institution might task a staff member with checking multiple dashboards at different times during the week to verify author affiliations, make APC payments, and gather data for reporting. These tools provide varying information and require a significant amount of human intervention throughout the entire publication process and later for reporting.

1.3 Summary

As described here, interviews with library staff revealed the following dynamics and challenges underlying open access workflows. They:

- are tailored to local conditions and shaped by numerous stakeholders and global factors;

- initially began as ad-hoc workflows and secondary tasks within the library, but have evolved and changed over time and are, in part, not yet fully integrated into library operations and structures;
- are carried out by a limited number of library staff tasked with what tends to be a growing number of responsibilities;
- require extensive knowledge to advise researchers navigating a complex open access landscape with various open access models;
- often involve redundancies, such as repeated entry of the same metadata; and
- rely on a multitude of publisher tools and intermediaries.

These dynamics underscore that genuine improvement in open access workflows requires coordination among various stakeholders in the scholarly publishing and library ecosystems. Priority should be given to automated processes, minimizing human intervention, while still enabling workflows to be integrated into central library structures and adaptable to local contexts.

2 Recommendations

Based on the information collected and discussed above, Transform2Open formulated recommendations for the optimization of open access processes. Given the multi-stakeholder nature of the system identified above, these recommendations address scholarly institutions and their libraries on the one hand, and negotiating and other library consortia on the other. Given that Transform2Open focuses on libraries and related institutions, we do not provide explicit recommendations for other stakeholders such as publishers. Nonetheless, some suggestions seek to influence cooperation with publishers, for example in recommendations for priorities during agreement negotiations.

The recommendations for libraries focus on areas where they have clear agency and where potential exists to optimize and reduce workloads. The recommendations for negotiating and other library consortia are structured somewhat differently. Apart from the first recommendation, which builds on existing ESAC and Alliance recommendations¹⁹, these are best understood as ideas and impulses for further exploration. Collaboration within consortia or during negotiations requires consensus among all parties involved and may often not be immediately actionable due to differing constraints.

2.1 Library/Institutional Level

RECOMMENDATION 1:

Routine assessment and adjustment of local open access processes in response to new developments and challenges

Libraries differ in size, institutional character, and needs and are at different stages in the development of their open access workflows. Regardless of these local contexts, the routine evaluation of local open access workflows allows libraries to document their processes and helps them identify ideas to respond to possible challenges. These reviews should examine how well open access work-

¹⁹ See footnotes 7 and 8.

flows are integrated into routine library operations and day-to-day workflows, and whether communication between the departments involved in open access workflows — including those outside the library — runs smoothly. A further important consideration is the evaluation of whether current structures and staffing can adequately support the (sometimes growing) workload required for open access workflows. Insights from these assessments may lead to the optimization or reduction of processes in other parts of the library, so as to allow for an adequate response to new demands. Libraries may even evaluate whether certain workflows might be phased out to recent developments.

RECOMMENDATION 2:

(Ongoing) Investment in Staff Training

Given the difficulties some institutions face when creating new positions to carry out open access responsibilities, Transform2Open recommends libraries invest in the training and professional development of their current staff at all levels. This can help ensure that the wide variety of open access responsibilities are effectively managed while also equipping personnel for future challenges.

Given the growing significance of open access, libraries should also consider in what way these trainings might not only benefit staff already working in the area of open access, but all library employees. As open access intersects with various areas of library work, fostering cross-departmental open access competencies through training can help distribute the workload more evenly and reduce the burden on specialized personnel.

RECOMMENDATION 3:

Investment in Software Solutions and Automation

Whenever possible, libraries should invest in automation and software solutions and/or contribute to the development of open source tools in this field. Automating routine tasks, such as metadata processing, can reduce workloads and the burden on staff.

Given ongoing personnel shortages, both generally and especially in open access positions, libraries should identify areas where software solutions by way of automation can mostly easily support open access workflows. While these investments may come with higher upfront costs, libraries should prioritize these solutions in light of the long-term gains they portend.

RECOMMENDATION 4:**Consideration of Agreements' Administrative Workloads**

When signing agreements that include open access components or Gold OA agreements, libraries should always consider the associated administrative workload.

Agreement administration is often labor-intensive, and these costs — just like publication fees — should be carefully evaluated. Given this, libraries are advised to strategically analyze agreements' associated workloads and prioritize the usage of standardized processes, such as collective invoicing and automated data flows (for example, by means of DeepGreen).

2.2 Consortial Level

RECOMMENDATION 5:**Open Articles and Open Metadata**

Transform2Open recommends that agreements with publishers include a) the required provision of open metadata, ideally with a CC0 license, and b) the delivery of full-text articles to open-access repositories. Ideally, these metadata should be made available in standardized formats (such as JATS) and include persistent identifiers (PIDs).²⁰

It is recommended that metadata exchange be a consistent priority in negotiations with publishers. Easy, central access to machine-readable and open metadata is a prerequisite for optimized and automated open access workflows. Therefore, it is recommended that future agreements require the deposit of standardized metadata records — enriched with a clearly defined set of PIDs — in shared infrastructure. These agreements would include the following:

- a. the delivery of metadata records, including financial information (for example, in the form of the openCost schema) and a predefined set of PIDs (see ESAC recommendations²¹, as well as the upcoming recommendations from the NISO Open Access Business Processes Working Group²²).

20 See the second commitment of the Barcelona Declaration (<https://barcelona-declaration.org/commitments>) and the recommendations of the Alliance of Science Organisations in Germany in footnote 8. The aforementioned recommendations apply not only to publish and read agreements but to all types of agreements, including pure publish agreements.

21 See footnote 7.

22 <https://niso.org/standards-committees/oabp>

- b. the deposit of this metadata in shared infrastructures such as Crossref and OA Switchboard as well as the delivery of metadata in a standardized, pre-defined format that libraries can access via APIs for use in internal processes.

RECOMMENDATION 6:

Use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

We recommend collaboration with publishers to increase the inclusion of PIDs in open access workflows in order to enhance the quality of (open access) publications' metadata. PIDs, particularly ORCID and ROR, should be embedded in metadata so as to better facilitate automated data flows.

RECOMMENDATION 7:

Standardization of Workflows for Affiliation Verification

In collaboration with other (international) stakeholders and publishers, the standardization of affiliation verification workflows ought to be pursued. For publication-intensive institutions with numerous publishing agreements and pledging commitments above all, a nationwide dashboard, populated via APIs from publishers, is an example of an initiative that could offer opportunities for optimization.

To contribute to the maintenance of “trusted identities”²³ in scholarly publishing and further increase the use of PIDs, it would also be beneficial to link the results of affiliation verification with the ORCID profiles of corresponding authors. With the explicit consent of profile owners, verified affiliation data could be displayed in their ORCID profiles to indicate that the information has been validated by the given institution.

RECOMMENDATION 8:

Enhanced Cost Monitoring Through Consortia

The central delivery of metadata, particularly financial metadata, from consortia to central infrastructures such as Open Access Monitor or OpenAPC is recommended. Currently, libraries allocate considerable personnel hours to collect

²³ See here the draft report from October 2024, “Trusted Identity in Academic Publishing: The Central Role of Digital Identity in Research Integrity,” <https://stm-assoc.org/new-stm-report-trusted-identity-in-academic-publishing/>.

and report out metadata from various publisher dashboards and budgetary systems (for example, SAP). This often involves the repetitive, manual or semi-automated entry of similar metadata spread across different institutions.

The delivery of this metadata from consortia in established reporting standards (e.g. the DFG Reporting Table, OpenAPC, and potentially the openCost schema) to institutions, would significantly reduce work burdens systemwide. One further option would be to explore the possibility of consortia depositing data directly — via an opt-in process by individual institutions — into OpenAPC, the Open Access Monitor, and other monitoring infrastructures. Although this presents challenges, particularly as some data is only available at the institutional level, it would be useful and advantageous if negotiating consortia, which benefit from these open data sources during contract negotiations, would play a more active role in maintaining these sources in the future.

RECOMMENDATION 9:

Investment and Collaboration

Transform2Open recommends that libraries collaboratively invest in shared software solutions and infrastructure, as well as host open access software solutions within sustainable, shared (infra)structures, possibly maintained by library consortia.

Robust, sustainably developed software solutions are essential for carrying out optimized open access workflows to support tasks such as the processing of machine-readable metadata, managing publication funds, and compiling reports.²⁴ To ensure these tools achieve widespread adoption, the ongoing development and integration of these software solutions in sustainable infrastructures must be prioritized — especially after the active development phase.

Libraries have long been active in consortia to centrally host catalogs with collective cataloging capabilities and provide hosting services for open access repositories. In the future, these consortia could offer an ideal framework in which to embed these tools, thereby ensuring that promising software developments with the potential to optimize open access workflows are sustainably supported by and accessible to all institutions, regardless of their size.

24 Some promising software solutions currently being developed include the FOLIO Open Access app, the software CODA developed by the ADoRE project (<https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/ub/ueber-uns/projektuebersicht/adore-oa>), and Output. For more on Output, see Bosse, S., Höhnow, T., Matthes, A., Stadler, H. (2025). Publikations- und Kosten-Monitoring in einem Software-Tool: Werkstattbericht zu einem Projekt der Universitätsbibliotheken Magdeburg und Potsdam. *Bibliotheksdienst* 59 (2), 126–137. <https://doi.org/10.1515/bd-2025-0021>.

3 Conclusion

These recommendations depict a future in which open access workflows are optimized and streamlined because they:

- are built upon established library structures;
- leverage current library staff equipped through training and professional development;
- activate the potential of library consortia and other networks and projects in collaborative software development;
- work with open standards at an international level; and
- strengthen cooperation within negotiating consortia, who actively call for open standards during agreement negotiations, thereby alleviating individual consortia members from resource-intensive processes.

Over the past two decades, open access processes have undergone a dynamic phase of experimentation and growth. These recommendations aim to build on this phase by encouraging libraries and consortia to embrace the challenge of a phase of consolidation. Consolidation does not herald the end of experimentation and growth, nor does it exclude new actors and smaller publishers. On the contrary: by adapting structures to a new open access reality and establishing open standards and automated reporting processes within sustainably managed, shared infrastructures, libraries can lay the foundation for more innovation, experimentation, and growth for all actors in the scholarly communication system, regardless of size.

Appendix: Question Catalog (in German)

1. Wie heißen Sie und wo arbeiten Sie?
2. Seit wann arbeiten Sie in dieser Einrichtung?
3. Welche Ausbildung haben Sie gemacht? (Bibliothekswissenschaft, Informationswissenschaft, usw.)
4. Seit wann unterstützt Ihre Einrichtung die Bezahlung von APCs? Hängt dieses Datum ggf. mit der Eröffnung des Publikationsfonds zusammen? Was passiert, wenn die DFG-Unterstützung reduziert wird?
5. Welche Verlagsvereinbarungen/Transformationsverträge hat Ihre Einrichtung/Universität? Gibt es einige, die ausgelaufen sind und nicht neu verhandelt wurden? Wenn ja, welche, und können Sie beschreiben warum?
6. Inwiefern fungiert Ihre Bibliothek als eine Zentralstelle für die Abwicklung von APC-Rechnungen für Ihre Einrichtung? Mit welchen Verlagen haben Sie diese Vereinbarung? Gibt es einige, wo sie diese Vereinbarung nicht haben? Wird die Bibliothek als zentrale Abwicklungsstelle für APCs angestrebt?
7. In welcher Abteilung (bzw. in welchen Abteilungen) werden OA-verbundene Prozesse durchgeführt (z.B. Dashboards von Verlagen bedient, Publikationsfonds verwaltet, Kostenmonitoring durchgeführt, DEAL-Prozesse verwaltet)? Wenn es mehrere Abteilungen gibt, die dafür zuständig sind, inwiefern kommunizieren/arbeiten sie miteinander? Arbeitet die Bibliothek im Rahmen dieser Tätigkeiten zusammen mit der Verwaltung oder weiteren Abteilungen der Universität?
8. Monitoren Sie sämtliche Publikationskosten Ihrer Institution? Gibt es zentrale Vorgaben für Buchungen von Publikationskosten innerhalb Ihrer Institution? (z.B. eigene Kostenart, Kostenstelle/Sachkonto, Angabe der DOI, usw.) Haben Sie Zugriff auf das Buchungssystem Ihrer Institution?
9. Verwenden Sie eine elektronische Rechnungsabwicklung und wenn ja, welche Formate benutzen Sie (z. B. XRechnung oder ZuGFerd)? Auf welchen

anderen Wegen und in welchen Formaten erhalten Sie Rechnungen zu Publikationskosten? Existiert dazu ein Workflow in Ihrer Institution?

10. Welche Werkzeuge benutzt Ihre Einrichtung, um diese verschiedenen Aktivitäten durchzuführen?
 - a. Dashboards? Welche? (OA Switchboard, Oable, ChronosHub, ...)
 - b. Exceltabellen?
 - c. Bibliotheksmanagementsystem? Wenn ja, welches?
 - d. Programme, die vor Ort entwickelt wurden?
 - e. Andere? (API, Automatisierung?)
11. Welche Metadaten sammeln Sie zum Zwecke des (Kosten)-Monitorings (bibliografische, juristische, technische, vertragliche, finanzielle, organisatorische; siehe <https://doi.org/10.2312/os.helmholtz.006>, S. 9–10)? Welche Metadaten werden automatisiert gesammelt und welche manuell? Sammeln Sie die Daten hinsichtlich des Jülicher Schemas (DFG-Kostenmonitoring) und/oder OpenAPC? Geben Sie die Daten an sonstige Stellen weiter, auch intern?
12. Verfügt Ihre Institution über ein Repositorium? Wenn ja,
 - a. Welches System? (DSpace, Opus, usw.)
 - b. Benutzen Sie Schnittstellen/APIs/Automatisierung, um Ihr Repositorium zu befüllen?
 - c. Welche Open-Access-Veröffentlichungen werden in das Repositorium aufgenommen? (Nur die, die durch den PF unterstützt wurden?; Alle Gold Open-Access?)
 - d. Haben Sie einen Workflow, um Zweitveröffentlichungen zu identifizieren und aufzunehmen? (Unabhängig von denen, die schon Diamond, Gold oder Hybrid sind?)
 - e. Hat Ihre Einrichtung Verlagsvereinbarungen, die “Automatic Deposit” in Ihr institutionelles Repositorium beinhalten?
13. Sind Sie mit dem openCost-Schema (siehe <https://www.opencost.de/metadaten-schema/>) vertraut? Wenn ja, haben Sie den Entwurf des Schemas kommentiert bzw. sind Sie mit dem jetzigen Stand des Schemas zufrieden? Können Sie sich vorstellen, dass dieses Schema Teil eines produktiven Workows werden könnte?
14. Was würden Sie sagen, funktioniert gut mit Ihrem System? (Welche drei...?)
15. Was würden Sie sagen, ist verbesserungsbedürftig? (Welche drei...?)